

Assessment of Awareness and Competency on Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy Among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, Nigeria

Bello Musa¹

Email: bellomusa1988@gmail.com

Tel: 08139591020

Suleiman Sani²

Email: sumar0102@gmail.com

Tel: 08069675575

Ismail Yusuf³

Email: ismailyusuf268d@gmail.com

Tel: 07069184469

¹ Department of Educational Foundation and Curriculum (Instruction Technology section), A.B.U. Zaria.

² Zamfara state Teachers Service Board Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

³ School of General Studies, College of Health Sciences and Technology Tsafe, Zamfara state, Nigeria

Abstract

This study assessment of awareness, and competency on integration of technology enhanced strategy among colleges of education pre-service teachers in Zamfara state. Two specific objectives guide the study; objectives were translated into research questions. Descriptive survey design was adopted with a population of 2952 pre-service teachers. The sample size for the study was 333 respondents which were selected using the research Advisor Table. Data were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to present the bio-data of the respondents while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The findings revealed that; the result obtained showed that pre-service teachers' are aware on integration of technology –enhanced strategy among colleges of education, and pre-service teachers are competent on integration of technology –enhanced strategy among colleges of education. The study recommended that, Management of Colleges of Education should organize additional workshop and training program for all Pre-service teachers' periodically, and more special training means for improving Pre-service teachers' competency in integration of technology.

Keywords: Awareness, Competency, and technology integration.

Introduction

The introduction of computer science as a subject in schools has been a focus on equipping students with the technological knowledge to use instruction technology resulting an improper use of instruction technology in the education domain (according to Cuban, 2001) Mua, (2016). Integrating technology in learning process, from the perspective is still in the introductory stage, making this necessary to find out how ICT is used as a tool to facilitate the learning process. Some teachers still actively resist the use of modern technology in teaching their students. Curricula are starting to emphasize capabilities and concerned more about how ICT can be utilized rather than on what ICT is. ICT in education can enhance learning environment for learners, act as a powerful tool to supplement teacher's classroom instructions, use as an administrative tool for teachers and administrators, increase access to education and inclusive education in schools Mua, (2016).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), created and used the "One Laptop Per Child" (OLPC) initiative as a means of closing the digital divide gap between developed and developing nations on the use of ICT. Though this action has dominated the front pages of many international organizations and countries as the top education agenda, the actual implementation and practice of this "One laptop per child" initiative have not yielded significant results especially in less developed countries Warschauer, and Ames, (2010). Nevertheless, the development of technology policies in Africa in particularly have often strives to match international ICT education policy. Despite the massive investment in the integration of ICT in many schools, the practical use of this ICT tools by teachers remains in a preliminary stage with little significant in the educational outcome Howie, (2010).

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Pfeffer, (2013). Pre-service teachers become competent when they perceived the usefulness in integrating technology enhanced learning. Competency in using ICT entails that Pre-service teachers' have to possess the skills, competence and capability in utilizing ICT gadgets that could be used to enhance students' comprehension and enables adequate retention and recall of concepts. ICT Competency Standards for Teachers (ICT-CST) overall goal is to improve teacher practice. It aims to achieve it in a way that contributes to a higher quality education system for a better-informed citizenry and higher quality workforce. It is against this background that this study intends to assess Pre-service teachers' Awareness, and Competency in Integration of Technology Enhanced Learning in Colleges of Education in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

1. Examine the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.
2. Evaluate the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Research Questions:

1. What is the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?
2. What is the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Methodology

This study adopted Descriptive Survey design, to collect detailed and true information that describes an existing phenomenon, Mustapha, (2015). It can also be seen as, the plan or proposal to conduct research, which involves the intersection of philosophy, strategies of inquiry and specific methods Hancock and Algozzine, (2016). The population of the study is two thousand nine hundred and fifty-two (2952) Pre-service teachers. The sample size used for the conduct of this study is three hundred and thirty-three (333) at 95% confidence level and 5.0% margin of error. The selection of this sample is based on the recommendation of research advisor (2006) who suggested that for population of 2500 to 3500 subjects, 333 subjects of the total population should be used as sample. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 333 respondents out of two (2) colleges of education in Zamfara state. The instrument for this study is structured questionnaire which was design by the Researcher. The Questionnaire was title; "Awareness, and Competency Instrument". With three sections; Sections; A, B, and C. Section: A obtain the respondents' general information while Section: B, and C is the items statements in relation to the objectives of the study using four (4) points modified Likert scale. The respondents were requested to indicate by ticking (√) in the appropriate boxes, the responses applicable to the items. After constructing the questionnaire, it is subjected to face, construct and content validity by specialists and experts in education from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education (Instruction Technology Section) Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The instrument was also pilot tested and the result was statistically analyzed for reliability co-efficient using Cronbach alpha at 0.05 level of significant. The reliability co-efficient of 0.81 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Based on this, the instrument was adjudged thus, the instrument is reliable and could be used for the study. The data collected on the Assessment of Awareness and Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to present the bio-data of the respondents while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Item 1-10 on the instrument were answered by the group of the respondents by ticking on either, Strongly Aware (SAW), Aware (AW), Not Aware (NAW) or Strongly Not Aware (SNA), and the researcher analyzed the responses using the mean and standard deviation as shown in the table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Participants on Awareness of Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy

S/N	Items	M	St.D	Decision
1.	I am aware of using computer applications in teaching.	3.66	0.56	AW
2.	I am aware of using search engine to access information about my research	3.66	0.70	AW
3.	I am aware of using Google scholar for research.	3.45	0.66	AW
4.	I am aware of using e-mail for sending and receiving information from my students	3.78	0.75	AW
5.	I am aware of using projector in teaching.	3.42	0.70	AW
6.	I am aware of using flash drive for storing my lecture note.	3.05	0.75	AW
7.	I am aware of using lecture note stored on CD-ROM for students to use for supplementary learning.	3.61	0.91	AW
8.	I am aware of using power point for lecture presentations.	3.70	0.52	AW
9.	I am aware of using WhatsApp group to promote collaborations between lecturers and students.	3.78	0.61	AW
10.	I am aware of using internet to download and use e-journal for research.	3.78	0.50	AW
Cumulative Mean		3.59	0.67	

Decision mean = 2.50

The overall mean score of all the responses is ($M=3.59/Std. = 0.67$) which is above 2.5 of decision rule which showed that majority of the respondents agree that pre-service teachers are aware in the integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Research Question 2:

What is the Competency on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State?

Item 11-20 on the instrument was answered by the group of the respondents by ticking on either Very Competent (VC), Competent (C), Fairly Competent (FC) or Not Competent (NC), and the researcher analyzed the responses using the mean and standard deviation as shown on the table 2

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Participants on Competency of Integration of Technology-Enhanced Strategy

S/N	Items	M	St.D	Decision
1.	I am competent in using computer applications in teaching.	3.71	0.51	C
2.	I am competent in using search engine to access information about my research	3.72	0.63	C
3.	I am competent in using Google scholar for research.	3.50	0.64	C
4.	I am competent in using e-mail for sending and receiving information from my students	3.79	0.70	C
5.	I am competent in using projector in teaching.	3.84	0.64	C
6.	I am competent in using flash drive for storing my lecture note.	3.46	0.55	C
7.	I am competent in storing lecture note on CD-ROM for students to use for supplementary learning.	3.50	0.85	C
8.	I am competent in using power point for lecture presentation.	3.18	0.49	C
9.	I am competent in using WhatsApp group to promote collaborations between lecturers and students.	3.83	0.54	C

10. I am competent in using internet to download and use e-journal for research.	3.79	0.48	C
Cumulative Mean	3.63	0.60	

Decision mean = 2.50

The overall mean score of all the responses is (M=3.63/Std. = 0.60) which is above 2.5 of decision rule which showed that majority of the respondents agree that Pre-service teachers are competent in integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one: The result revealed that more than 94% of the respondents are aware of integration Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State. The finding presented in mean and standard deviation for each item indicated that the respondents agree with the majority of the item, statements. The reason being that, items 1 to 10 having the mean of 3.08 to 3.84 respectively fall within the a priori expectation 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.63 is also above the decision mean of 2.50 of this study. It implies that level of Pre-service teachers' Awareness on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State is positive. Some variables relevant to this question were analyzed with a view to provide objective analysis. This finding is not alone but in line with the result of Tabassu, and Shehzadi, (2018), state that faculty members of the public sector women universities of Pakistan are aware of the requirement and significance of ICTs in education sector. They have positive attitude towards computers and age is one of the major factors which affect the attitude.

Research question two: The result reveals that Pre-service teachers are competent on integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State, 95% of the respondents agree with the majority of the item, statements. The reason being that, items 21 to 30 having mean of 3.00 to 3.84 respectively fall within the a priori expectation 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.24 is also above the decision mean of 2.50. The cumulative mean of 3.24 is also above the decision mean of 2.50. This finding is not in line with the result of Tabassu, & Shehzadi, (2018), states that the competence level of using computers is low. Most of the faculty members of the Public Sector Women Universities of Pakistan have never attended any training regarding ICTs not even a single time. Folorunso, (2010) Observed that; mass un awareness, low computer literacy level, and cost were identified as critical factors affecting the acceptability of Information and Communication Technology by the teachers of Nigerian Institutions. These results are not consistent with this study.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the present study; the study concluded that; Pre-service teachers are aware on the needs to integrate technology to enhanced learning, in colleges of education in Zamfara state, Nigeria. The study centered on Pre-service teachers in the colleges of education in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made;

1. Management of Colleges of Education should organize additional workshop and training program for all Pre-service teachers' periodically.
2. College administrators should organize more special training means for improving Pre-service teachers' competency in integration of technology.

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